

THE BEGINNING OF THE UPRISINGS OF THE SKOBELEV REGION**SHAKHZODKHUJA ABDURAZZAKOV**

Namangan State University

4th year student of History

shaxzodxojaabdurazzaqov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139603>

Annotation: As a result of the publication in this work of the decree of the Russian emperor on mobilization for Labor, brief information was given about the attitude of the residents of Skobelev uyezdi and the beginning of the initial popular uprisings against this decree, as well as the beginning of this uprising, based on recorded data from active participants in this.

Keywords: A.Ya. Pakhotin, Qalandarkhana, Mavlon Laylayev, Qasimkhoja Yusufalikhojayev, Muzaffar Gafurov, Khamid military, Newgarden, Makhmudbek and Mavlonbek.

The territory of Skobelev uyezd in the Fergana region was 14,069 sq km, which included 21 volosts and the city of Margilan. The uprisings in other uyezds also covered Skobelev uyezdi. The first uprising in uyezd began on July 10 in the city of Margilan, uyezd Center. According to archival documents on this day, the city police officer Lieutenant Colonel A.Ya.Pakhotin wanted to gather all the city's fifties into the Ordatagi Square and explain the content of the Tsar's decree. At this time, by phone, pristav reports that in the Ordataghi Square, in addition to the fifties, a large crowd of people stood.

After that, the polytheist will take the elders, pristavs and police officers of all geniuses and arrive at Urdatagi Square at 9:00 AM early. A.Ya. Pakhotin walks past the crowd in action and goes out into the teahouse Supa. The noise-raising crowd shouted A.Ya.Did not let pahotin speak. After 10 minutes in the same alphabet, the crowd surrounds him in a circle and beats him. Pristav shoots his revolver and somehow gets out of the crowd. He goes out from the back of the cafeteria, rides a horse and tries to cross it towards the Horde through the market. On the way, he is joined by three police officers and the elder of the part of the penthouse. There was not a living soul there when it came to the Horde. There were only 4 elders, the police and the dead of the guards lying on the ground. The crowd had done the job in 1.5-2 minutes[1.97-98].

Tajiboy Madaliyev, who took an active part in the uprising, remembers him like this: "...I and the other numerous "old choppers", khashakfurush began an attack on officials. We killed Mavlonbek and Mahmudbek mingbashi under the crowd. In the same manner had an English mirshabi and a police starshiyya dam killed. After that, I broke into the movie building, which was located in the Horde with

my own damrod, chasing a policeman. Here personally, I myself took out a picture of King Nicholas hanging on the wall and kicked it. After that, I and my comrades returned to our neighborhood. On this day, in the evening, the Cossack soldiers from Fergana arrived in Margilan, took the rebels under a bat and rested. The Cossack soldiers beat us with creamy sticks in such a way that we lost our temper. The body of the punished was stained with blood and badly injured"[2.99-100].

Another of the active participants in the uprising, Mavlon Laylayev, describes the uprising as follows: "in the morning about 20 thousand people gathered in the Horde. Officials of the Tsarist government and the local rich soon arrived here, also holding paper in their hands. Then Madmudbeck, looking at the people, said, " the sky is high and the Earth is hard, so you cannot escape from us anywhere, you are obliged to go to Labor"[3.75-76]... Then the uprising began. I was the first to knock Madmudbeck mingbashi to the ground and now that you're caught, I didn't make a hissing sound because I strangled my throat with both hands. At this moment, the crowd struck and killed the Mingachevir with axes, stones and steppes. After that, I went with a bunch of companions, saying that we would burn the House of Mahmudbek and rob him of his property.

In the previous ranks of the lambgolonists, I was going. Hence. on the way to Khamid mirshab fired at me, but the bullet did not touch me... The crowd also beat Hamid mirshab with stones and bricks in birpas and smashed. Another Cossack, mirshabi, came upon what we were doing, put a sword on me and wounded my neck. Immediately, my comrades sprinkled soil around my neck and tied it with a belt. And the Cossack mirshabi escaped... After the uprising, I fled to the village of Usaq, to my stepfather. A peasant who fell into the city the next day informed me that if they did not find me, they would punish all the inhabitants of the city with the death penalty. When I heard this news, I returned to the city and was imprisoned, saying that the shahr people would not be exterminated because of one. Having tied my limbs at the court in New York, eleven times the Cossack soldats hit me on the ground like a ball[4.107-108]"

Thus, the struggle of the people against the Tsarist government was also expressed in the punishments they imposed on the mingbash, elders, etc., made up of its local officials. About this, the participant of the uprising, Rachman Razzakov, recalls: "they would raise sticks with a scarf around the end of the crowd to the sky and shout that we would not go to labor, but shoot. The crowd attacked officials and killed Makhmudbek and Mavlonbek. I saw with my own eyes the death of the Mingachevir of Makhmudbek being petrified by wives. I

myself also take a direct part in the murder of millennials. People would stand on top of the mingbashi and thank God that we have saved the wrongdoers”[5.121-123]

An important place in the organization of the uprising was taken by the influential people of the city Kasymkhoja Yusufalikhojayev, the judge of the Kalandarkhana, and his brothers Umarkhon and Mukarramkhans. Mukarram Khan in particular served greatly for the benefit of the people. He had urged the crowd to raise their heads by running a neighborhood-neighborhood horse the night before the uprising. He describes the beginning of the uprising as follows: “after the propaganda of Mukarram Khan, that is, after the morning of fasting, the crowd gathered in front of the police station located in the new park and demanded the exit of the Tsarist government officials. But they were afraid and did not appear to the fall of the people. After that, the crowd came to Jarmasjid from the inside of the Galandarkhana. A lot of people were gathering here too. All of us asked Qasimhoja Qazi, “why don't you go against injustice while you are a judge?!”when we demanded the truth, he could not stand our side and went with us to Saidakhmadhoja zavodchinski. The fabricator was one of the largest influential people in the rich city and was one of the supporters of obtaining labor. Saidakhmadhoja fled to Fergana, knowing that the crowd around 4-5 thousand was coming against him. There were also workers working at his factory in the crowd”[6.110]

So, the uprising began at first in the hut of the penthouse. From here, the crowd went to his house to punish Saidakhmadhaja, a promoter of mobilizing for Labor. When they could not find him, they went to the Horde Square in the city. Here their rebellion has multiplied tirelessly. "We," says Kimsan Abrokhimov, "when we came to the Horde, we saw a large number of people crying there too. Soon after that, a man in an old ragged robe, before reading the decree of one of the Tsarist government officials to be promoted, was thrown over the shoulders of the poor, crawling over the shoulders, reading the decree, and plucked the paper from his hand. And the official could not shoot at him.

The rebels were agitated against the officials. And when I saw that they were trying to call a soldier from Fergana by phone from the mid-police Budka, we cut off the telephone wire with Muzaffar Gafurov. The disconnection of the telephone wires and the inability of the soldates to arrive in time, as a result, made it possible to immediately disperse people and keep them from the axis of the militaries.

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